

Antitachycardia Pacing: Averting Shock!

Mohammad As Sayaideh, M.D.^a, Alexis Parks, D.O.^a, Sanchitha Nagaraj, M.D.^a, Hajira Malik, M.D.^a,
Brent Ruiz, M.D.^a, Celestine Odigwe, M.D.^a, Mashal Mumtaz, M.D.^b,
Bassam Omar, M.D., Ph.D.^{a,c}, Suganya Monoharan, M.D.^a, Christopher Malozzi, D.O.^a

Description

The above 12-lead electrocardiograms (ECG) were obtained in a patient with severe non-ischemic cardiomyopathy with an implantable defibrillator. The onset of sustained ventricular tachycardia (VT) is evident in Figure A (red arrow) with a short cycle length. Shortly after, in Figure 2, the defibrillator initiates rapid ventricular anti-tachycardia pacing (ATP) at a cycle length shorter than that of the VT (red arrow), in an attempt to overdrive pace the VT. The pacemaker spikes can be seen together with a shift in axis indicative of satisfactory capture of the ventricles. This resulted in restoring sinus tachycardia with left bundle branch block, seen in Figure C, thereby averting a defibrillator shock.

Discussion

Implantable defibrillators provide life-saving shocks which terminate a variety of lethal ventricular arrhythmias [1]; they have been associated with improved survival. The psychological distress of a defibrillator shock, or its anticipation, however, is enormous resulting in various forms of anxiety and depression, and poor quality of life [2].

ATP introduced a less traumatic option for the termination of ventricular tachycardia, avoiding shocks [3]. Characteristics related to the patient, the device or its programming can determine the ATP success [4]. VT acceleration is one potential negative side effect of ATP, especially in very fast VTs, which may require subsequent defibrillation [5]; this can be mitigated by avoidance of ramp pacing and delivery of shorter ATP bursts in fast VTs.

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a Division of Cardiology. University of South Alabama,
Mobile, AL 36617

b Department of Internal Medicine, University
College of Medicine and Dentistry, Lahore, Pakistan

c Corresponding Author: Bassam Omar, Division of
Cardiology, University of South Alabama, 2451 USA
Medical Center Dr., Mobile, AL 36617, USA.

Email: bomar@health.southalabama.edu

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